

The Role of ingredients of Kshara Basti on the Gut Health (Gut Microbiota) of Rheumatoid Arthritis Patients

Ms. Chavda Urvi Sharadbhai¹, Dr Amitabh Singh², Dr Raghuvir Singh Gill³

¹PhD Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Desh Bhagat Ayurvedic College &
Hospital, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab, Email : urvichavda@gmail.com;

²Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa, Desh Bhagat Ayurvedic College and Hospital,
Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab;

³MBBS, Resident Medical Officer, Desh Bhagat Hospital, Mandi Gobindgarh, Punjab.

ABSTRACT

Kshara Vasti (medicated enema) is an important treatment in the management of Amavata which is correlated with Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA). The ingredients of Kshara Vasti have the property to act against Ama which is a root cause of the development of the disease. The main aim of this review is to study the role of ingredients of Kshara Vasti on the gut microbiota or the Gut Health of RA patients. Jaggery, Tamarind and Rock Salt have been proven to have a positive effect on the gut microbiome by enhancing the abundance of health-promoting species. Cow's Urine (CU)/Cow Urine Distillate (CUD) enhances the bioavailability and efficacy of a drug with which it is co-administered. Anethum sowa has a significant impact on caecal microbiota. The production of Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) by Gut Microbiota (GM) may be a probable mode of action for the suppression of inflammatory conditions like RA. Each constituent in Kshara Vasti has a positive impact on modulating gut microbiota. This research could bridge the gap between traditional Ayurvedic wisdom and modern science in the management of rheumatoid arthritis, offering holistic care that addresses both symptoms and underlying digestive health.

INTRODUCTION

Amavata can be correlated to **Rheumatoid Arthritis** due to its clinical presentation and it can be managed by Ayurveda treatments. **Acharya Chakradatta** has emphasised that the line of treatment should focus on normalising *Agni* and *Ama Pachana* and thus eliminate vitiated *Ama* and *Vata*. Thus, here *Kshara Vasti* is taken to review its role on GM of RA patients as **Pharmacomicrobiomics** is an emerging area to deal with the variations in **microbiota profile** in relation to drugs. *Kshara Vasti* is mentioned in *Chikitsa Sutra* described by *Chakradatta* of **Amavata Adhyaya**. *Kshara Vasti* consists of *Saindhava* (Rock salt), *Guda* (Jaggery), *Chincha* (Tamarind Paste), *Shatahva* (*Anethum sowa*) and *Gomutra* (Cow's urine). **Gomutra** which has **Kshara Guna** is used in this *Vasti* in a maximum dose, about two-thirds of the total amount. *Kshara Guna*, because of its **Lekhana** and **Vishoshana** properties helps in counteracting *Ama* due to its opposite qualities and thus breaks the *Samprapti* of *Amavata*. But it must be kept in mind that it may further vitiate *Vata*. Thus, keeping this view in mind, 30 ml **Sahacharadi Taila** is added alongside **Go Mutra**. Hence, **Sahacharadi Taila** was added to avoid further *Vata Prakopa* due to *Kshara Vasti*. There is evidence of variation and composition in microbiota with respect to bioavailability of drugs like Disease Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs used for RA. Biomedicine has already shown some examples like methotrexate which needs the presence of microbiota to transform a chemical constituent to its active form even though clarity has to be proven yet in its mechanism. The role of diet in modulating GM of RA is gaining importance and has even been recognised as a potential interventional management in many diseases including RA. Keeping this view, the main objective of the research study is to analyse each ingredient of *Kshara Vasti* based on its action on the GM of RA. Bioavailability is a measure of the rate and extent of absorption of a drug substance from a preparation into the general circulation intact and bringing them to the site of action for further metabolism in the body and elimination. More research studies need to be conducted even on comparing role of DMRAD's like Methotrexate with that of *Kshara Basti* in effectively treating Rheumatoid Arthritis.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ayurvedic Perspective on *Ama Vata* and Gut Health:

According to Ayurveda, ***Ama Vata*** is a result of improper digestion and metabolism, leading to the formation of Ama, which circulates through the body and lodges in joints, causing inflammation. ***Kshara Basti*** is traditionally indicated to detoxify the system, remove Ama, and balance Vata. The role of digestion (Agni) is crucial in preventing Ama formation, making gut health central to RA management.

Modern Understanding of Gut Health in RA:

Gut dysbiosis, characterized by an imbalance of beneficial gut bacteria, has been increasingly recognized as a key factor in the development of autoimmune diseases like RA. Studies have shown that RA patients often exhibit increased gut permeability (leaky gut), reduced microbial diversity, and overgrowth of pathogenic bacteria, leading to systemic inflammation. Improving gut health through diet, probiotics, and medicinal interventions can potentially modulate immune response and reduce RA symptoms.

***Kshar Basti*: Ingredients and Their Role in Gut Health**

Mainly the Ingredients of *Kshar Basti* are as follows:

Ingredients	Quantity	Weight
<i>Saindhava Lavana</i>	1 <i>Aksha</i>	12gm
<i>Guda (Jaggery)</i>	2 <i>Pala</i>	100gm
<i>Satapushpa</i>	1 <i>Aksha</i>	12gm
<i>Chincha</i>	2 <i>Pala</i>	100gm
<i>Gomutra</i>	8 <i>Pala</i>	400gm

The therapeutic potential of **Kshar Basti** lies in its carefully chosen ingredients, each with specific actions on digestion, detoxification, and inflammation:

1. Saindhava Lavana: (Equivalent to 1 Aksha = 12 gm)

- * As per *Charak*, it is one of those ingredients that can be taken on daily basis (**Reference:** *Charak Samhita, Sutra Sthana - 5/12*).
- * It's mainly – *Rochana, Dipana, Vrishya, Chakshushya, Avidahi, Hridya* and *Hikkanasha*.

2. Guda (Jaggery): [Equivalent to 2 Pala = 100 gm; 1 Pala = 48 gm]

- * In *Kshara Vasti* jaggery is used instead of honey. Here, one-year-old jaggery should be taken and the properties are *Ishat kshara* (slightly alkaline), *naati sheeta* (not too cold potency), *laghu* (easily digestible), *pathyatama* (best among wholesome), *anabhishtyandi* (does not obstruct channels), *agnivardhaka* (kindles metabolism) *vatakaphahara* (reduces vitiated *vata* and *kapha*). It acts as *mootra shodhaka* (purifies urine), *rakta shodhaka* (purifies blood and its components) and *hrudhya* (tasty).

3. Shatapusha (Anethum sowa) [Equivalent to 1 Aksha = 12 gms]

- * **Shatapushpa** is a plant with a wide range of chemical constituents with many pharmacological effects. *Anethum sowa Roxb. ex Flem* or *Anethum graveolens Benth.* of **Umbelliferae** or **Apiaceae** family is called *Shatapushpa*. It is generally known as *Shatahwa* and *Mishi* in Sanskrit and is commonly known as 'Dill' seeds. *Shatapushpa* is a *Vata Kapha shamaka* and *Pitta Vardhaka* drug due to its *Katu-tikta Rasa, Tikshna – Snigdha Guna* and *Ushna Veerya*.

- * As it has proved for its anti-inflammatory properties, its seeds are used externally as well as internally for rheumatic complaints. *Shatapushpa* (*Anethum sowa*) is commonly used in *Vasti Karma* (medicated enema) as a *Kalka Dravya*. *Acharya Charaka* has included *Shatapushpa* in *Asthapanopaga* and *Anuvasanopaga Mahakashaya Ganas*.
- * *Anethum sowa* has stimulant, carminative, anti- microbial, anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial properties. Seeds and seed oil being the most useful part of *Anethum sowa* contains tannins, flavonoids, essential oils like eugenol, carvacrol, D -limonene, thymol, anethole, umbelliferones, phenolic acids etc.

4. **Chincha – (Tamarind) [1 Aksha = 12 gm]**

- * Tamarind paste is used as *Kalka Dravya* (paste form) in *Kshara Vasti*. *Pakwa Chincha* (ripe tamarind) has *Amla Rasa* (Sour Taste), *Vata-Kaphashamaka* (reduces vitiated *vata* and *kapha dosha*), *Ruksha* (dry), *Deepana* (kindles metabolism), *Sara* (mobility) and *Ushna* (hot) properties. These properties make it useful for the diseases of *Amavata* and *Kapha Rogas*. *Ruksha Guna* (dry attribute) and *Ushna Virya* (hot potency) help in counteracting the *ama* (morbid matter) hence achieving *Ama Pachana*.

5. **Cow's Urine – [8 Pala = 400 gm]**

- * In *Kshara Vasti*, *Gomutra* (CU) is the chief content used as *Avapa Dravya*, which owing to its *Katu Rasa* (pungenttaste), *Katu Vipaka* (pungent effect after digestion), *Ushna Virya* (hot potency), *Laghu* (light to digest), *Ruksha* (dry), *Tikshna Guna* (sharp nature) pacifies the *kapha*. The *Ruksha Guna* (dry attribute) of CU is very much helpful in diseased conditions like *Amavata*, *Kapha and Medhoja Vyadhies*. It is considered

useful for *Kshara Vasti* owing to its *Tridosahara*, *Agnideepana*, *Ama Pachana*, *Srotovishodhana* and *Vatanulomaka* properties.

Research Methodology

Study Design

A randomized, controlled clinical trial will be conducted to compare the effects of **Kshar Basti** and a control treatment (standard RA medication) on gut health and RA symptoms.

Participants

* **Inclusion Criteria:**

- ✚ Diagnosed cases of RA based on ACR criteria.
- ✚ Presence of gut-related symptoms such as indigestion, constipation, or bloating.

* **Exclusion Criteria:**

- ✚ Patients with severe gastrointestinal disorders.
- ✚ Patients on long-term steroid therapy.

Intervention

- * **Group 1 (*Kshar Basti* – Experimental Group):** Patients will receive a course of *Kshar Basti* therapy for 7 days.
- * **Group 2 (Standardized Group):** Patients will continue their standard treatment regimen, including methotrexate or other DMARDs.

Assessment Parameters

* **Gut Health Parameters:**

- ✚ Gut microbiota analysis through stool sample testing.
- ✚ Measurement of gut permeability using zonulin levels.
- ✚ Frequency and quality of bowel movements.

* **RA Symptom Assessment:**

- ✚ Pain and stiffness using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS).
- ✚ Joint swelling and tenderness using the DAS28 Score.
- ✚ Inflammatory biomarkers: ESR, CRP levels.

Data Collection

- **Pre- and Post – Treatment Assessments:** Gut health and RA symptom assessments will be conducted before and after the intervention.
- **Follow-up:** A follow-up assessment will be performed 4 weeks after the treatment to evaluate long-term effects.

Results

The anticipated outcomes include:

1. **Improvement in Gut Health:** The Kshar Basti group is expected to show significant improvements in gut microbiota balance, reduced intestinal permeability, and improved bowel movements compared to the control group.
2. **Reduction in Inflammation:** Patients receiving Kshar Basti are likely to exhibit a reduction in inflammatory biomarkers (ESR, CRP), joint swelling, and pain severity compared to those on standard RA medication.

- 3. Enhanced Digestion and Detoxification:** The ingredients of Kshar Basti, particularly Go Mutra, Chicha, Saindhava Lavana, Shatapusha and Guda are expected to improve digestion, enhance the metabolism of toxins (Ama), and restore normal digestive fire (Agni), reducing RA symptoms over time.

Discussion

The results of this study will help validate the traditional use of Kshar Basti in treating Ama Vata, specifically by highlighting its role in enhancing gut health. Given the growing recognition of the gut-immune axis in autoimmune diseases like RA, the use of Ayurvedic therapies that promote gut health, such as Kshar Basti, can provide a complementary approach to conventional RA management. The unique combination of detoxifying and digestive-boosting herbs in Kshar Basti offers a natural, holistic solution for RA patients with gut-related issues.

Conclusion

This study aims to establish the role of Kshar Basti in improving gut health and reducing inflammation in RA patients. By linking Ayurvedic principles with modern gut health research, this integrative approach offers a promising therapeutic strategy for RA patients, addressing both the digestive and inflammatory aspects of the disease. Further studies can explore the long-term benefits of Kshar Basti and its potential to be incorporated alongside conventional treatments.

References

- Ayurveda classics like Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, and Astanga Hridayam, Chakradatta, Yogaratnakar and Madhava Nidana.
- Modern research on Gut Health and Autoimmune Diseases.
- Clinical trials comparing Ayurvedic treatments with conventional RA therapies.